

Effectiveness of Self-Talk Training to Improve Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation, and Performance of Venus Angels Futsal Athletes Semarang

Slamet Alamsyah¹, Agus Kristiyanto², Fadilah Umar³, Slamet Riyadi⁴

^{1,2,3,4} Sports Science Study Program, Faculty of Sports, Universitas Sebelas Maret, Indonesia

^{1,2,3,4} Ir. Sutami Street Number 36, Kentingan, Kec. Jebres, Surakarta City, Central Java 57126, Indonesia

ORCID ID: 0009-0001-3535-3872¹, 0000-0001-7961-4643², 0000-0003-3371-2613³, 0000-0002-6403-7051⁴

ABSTRACT:

Purpose: This study aims to determine the Effectiveness of Self-Talk Training to Improve Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation, and Performance of Venus Angels Futsal Athletes Semarang.

Materials and Methods: The type of research used in this study is a type of quantitative research using pre-experimental methods. The design in this study used a one group pretest-posttest. The normality test uses the Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality Test with the rule that if the value (p) > 0.05 then it is normally distributed. Meanwhile, if the value (p) < 0.05 then the data is abnormally distributed. This normality test is analyzed using the help of the computer program SPSS for windows version 25. The homogeneity test uses the Levene's Test, aiming to determine the variation of the initial sample data, with the rule that if the value of (p) > 0.05 then the data group has a homogeneous variant, on the contrary if the value of (p) < 0.05 then the data group has a heterogeneous variant. This homogeneity test is analyzed using the help of the SPSS for windows version 25 computer program. Test the hypothesis was carried out using the T-test and the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test.

Results: Based on the results of the research that has been done and looking at the statistical descriptive data, it shows that there is an increase in the average before and after being given the Self Talk Training treatment of each variable, namely self-confidence, achievement motivation and athlete performance. The results of the research data from the results of the pretest and posttest of confidence with a sample of 16 athletes, obtained an average pretest data of 52.3125 with a standard deviation of 3.85951 and an average posttest data of 59.0625 with a standard deviation of 3.51129. The achievement motivation variable shows the results of the research data from the pretest and posttest results with a sample of 16 athletes, obtained an average pretest data of 29.6250 with a standard deviation of 2.65518 and a posttest average data of 34.5000 with a standard deviation of 2, 47656. The performance variable shows the results of research data from the pretest and posttest results with a sample of 16 female athletes, obtained an average pretest data of 72.7500 with a standard deviation of 6.45497 and a posttest average data of 76.3125 with a standard deviation of 2, 47656.

Conclusions: Based on the results of the research and the results of the data analysis conducted, it shows that there was a significant increase before and after being given the Self Talk Training treatment of each variable, namely self-confidence, achievement motivation and athlete performance. After being analyzed with the T-test and Wilcoxon signed rank test, it was concluded that Self-Talk Training was effective in increasing self-confidence, achievement motivation, and performance of futsal athletes of Venus Angels Semarang. Participants before and after being given the intervention. The tests above prove that Self-Talk Training is effective in increasing self-confidence, achievement motivation, and performance of futsal athletes of Venus Angels Semarang.

KEYWORDS: Effectiveness, Self-Talk Training, Self-Confidence, Motivation, Performance, Futsal

INTRODUCTION

Futsal is one of the most popular games that is currently in great demand by the people of Indonesia (Sari, 2016). Futsal is a sport that is played indoors which is similar or similar to football, each team consists of five core players and is different from soccer which has 11 players (Aguss & Yuliandra, 2021). The size of the futsal field is 20x40m, different from the size of a football field.

Effectiveness of Self-Talk Training to Improve Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation, and Performance of Venus Angels Futsal Athletes Semarang

Venus Angels is one of the women's futsal clubs in the city of Semarang. It has a secretariat located on Jalan Prof. Suharso Sendang Mulyo Semarang. Venus Angels Semarang was formed on February 20 2015 with director Andri Surya Putra, head coach Paulus Chandra O, assistant coach Fikie Saputra, S.Pd, and goalkeeping coach Mulky Mughty. Many players from various schools, colleges and locales have joined the Venus Angels club. The existence of the Venus Angels Semarang futsal club is believed to be able to advance women's futsal in Central Java, especially the city of Semarang.

Venus Angels Semarang is also a place to develop futsal skills, this is evidenced by the practice every Monday and Wednesday at the Venus Sendangmulyo futsal field in Tembalang. In relation to coaching to increase the capacity of athletes, especially futsal players, training is needed. According to (Suriani & Lesmana, 2019) Good training is a systematically planned activity by following the different game attributes, time accessibility, and the athletes to be coached. The harmonious development of athletes between physically and mentally is very necessary to achieve maximum performance (Jamalong, 2014). Increasing physical, technical and tactical abilities without mental coaching will result in negative results because mentality is the driving force and driving force to strengthen physical, technical and tactical abilities in sports performance.

Confidence and achievement motivation is one thing that is very important and needed to achieve maximum performance, if an athlete has low self-confidence and achievement motivation it will greatly affect the athlete's performance during competition (Walid et al., 2019). Self-confidence and achievement motivation are very serious problems for Venus Angels players in the several tournaments they have participated. In the official tournament organized by the provincial futsal association (AFP), Venus Angels has never won first place.

Sports confidence is confidence applied to sporting situations (Apriansyah et al., 2017). Self-confidence has always been considered a very important factor affecting sports performance (Nisa & Jannah, 2021). People who are confident in sports refer to those who have the confidence to be able to acquire the physical abilities and sports skills appropriate to the tasks required for sports (Sakti & Rozali, 2015).

Motivation is an individual's actions, thoughts and feelings that arise by emphasizing something in him (Muhammad, 2017). Motivation comes from the Greek word: "movere" means "to move" which means to push and move (Masni, 2015). Regarding the objectives a player wants to accomplish in order to perform at their best and reach their goals, futsal players truly need motivation (Effendi, 2016).

(Rohaeni, 2016) have the opinion that motivation can be interpreted as a driving force and strength to be able to do certain things. In line with this opinion, whether or not the target of a goal is achieved is a very strong role of motivation itself (Sri Murniyanti, 2020). Motivation is also a psychological energy whose form is abstract and can only be understood and observed in how individuals behave (Fadillah, 2013). Motivation is a psychological process of reflection on the strength of the interaction between experience and cognition (Nopiyanto & Dimiyati, 2018).

Self talk training has not been used in the training process for the Venus Angels team, which causes negative self talk among the Venus Angels players. (Fitria, 2018) found that self-talk is a mental training program proposed by sports psychologists with the hope of regulating emotions, cognition, behavior and performance. An athlete who has positive self-talk can play with confidence and achievement motivation from every athlete in facing a competition is also very important to be able to support his performance on the field (Putra & Jannah, 2017). Training on the effectiveness of self-talk focuses more on one of the most important mental trainings in futsal, because futsal matches are clean for 20 minutes in each round, and 2 rounds in each match do not only rely on physical strength alone, a good mentality is wrong. one thing is very important to be able to play optimally and win matches (Marhani et al., 2018).

Great performance determines the achievement of an athlete in a match. Performance is a non-verbal correspondence, and is something that is important to be prepared for, proper performance must be compatible with physical and emotional health (Rahmansyah et al., 2021). Execution in sport has been the subject of mental examination for over a hundred years, providing results on motivation, perception, stress, self-confidence, mental organization, and group elements.

(Gustian, 2016) explains that the athlete's appearance is something that is seen or displayed by athletes on the field. Performance or appearance is a condition that athletes have when carrying out all forms of sports activities when competing (Ulfah, 2006). Appearance is a very important aspect to review, both when an athlete loses or wins (Wan Norina Wan Hamat, Zaharah Hussin, Ahmad Fakrudin Mohamed Yusoff, 2013). Victory can be obtained due to the luck factor, and an athlete who is lulled in his victory, will make the athlete pay less attention to his appearance.

Based on the description of the factors mentioned above, it is known that the self-talk method is one of the training methods that can be chosen to increase self-confidence, achievement motivation, and performance of futsal athletes. However, it is not yet known how effective the self-talk method is in increasing self-confidence, achievement motivation, and the performance of futsal athletes. To know for sure, it is necessary to conduct research by providing self-talk methods to increase

Effectiveness of Self-Talk Training to Improve Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation, and Performance of Venus Angels Futsal Athletes Semarang

self-confidence, achievement motivation, and performance of futsal athletes. Based on the background of the problems that have been described, the researcher will conduct a study entitled "Effectiveness of Self Talk Training to Increase Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation, and Performance of Futsal Venus Angels Semarang Athletes".

METHOD

The type of research used in this study is a type of quantitative research using pre-experimental methods. The design in this study used a one group pretest-posttest. (Andrini & Pratama, 2021) explained that the one group pretest-posttest design is a research activity that gives an initial test (pretest) before being given treatment, after being given treatment then gives a final test (posttest). This one group pretest-posttest design consists of one predetermined group. In this design, the test was carried out twice, namely before being given the treatment is called the pre-test and after the treatment is called the post-test. As for the research pattern of the one group pretest-posttest design according to (Sugiyono, 2019) as follows:

Table 1. Research Design

Pre Test	Treatment	Post Test
z1	x	z2

Information:

z1 : Pre test confidence, achievement motivation, and performance.

z2 : Post test confidence, achievement motivation, and performance.

X : The use of self-talk exercises to increase self-confidence, achievement motivation, and performance.

The normality test uses the Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality Test with the rule that if the value (p) > 0.05 then it is normally distributed. Meanwhile, if the value (p) < 0.05 then the data is abnormally distributed. This normality test is analyzed using the help of the computer program SPSS for windows version 25. The homogeneity test uses the Levene's Test, aiming to determine the variation of the initial sample data, with the rule that if the value of (p) > 0.05 then the data group has a homogeneous variant, on the contrary if the value of (p) < 0.05 then the data group has a heterogeneous variant. This homogeneity test is analyzed using the help of the SPSS for windows version 25 computer program. Test the hypothesis was carried out using the T-test and the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test.

RESULT

Table 2. Data Description

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
GPB	16	72,7500	6,45497	64,00	85,00
GPA	16	76,3125	5,51022	68,00	88,00
MotB	16	29,6250	2,65518	26,00	36,00
MotA	16	34,5000	2,47656	32,00	40,00
KepB	16	52,3125	3,85951	47,00	60,00
KepA	16	59,0625	3,51129	54,00	66,00

Based on the results of the research data from the pretest and posttest results of self-confidence with a sample of 16 female athletes Venus Angels, the pretest average data was 52.3125 with a standard deviation of 3.85951 and the posttest average data was 59.0625 with a standard deviation 3.51129. The highest self-confidence pretest score is 60.00 and the lowest score is 47.00 while the highest self-confidence posttest score is 66.00 and the lowest score is 54.00.

Based on the results of the research data from the pretest and posttest results of achievement motivation with a sample of 16 Venus Angels female athletes, the pretest average data was 29.6250 with a standard deviation of 2.65518 and the posttest average data was 34.5000 with a standard deviation 2.47656. The highest pretest score for achievement motivation was 26.00 and the lowest score was 36.00 while the highest posttest score for achievement motivation was 32.00 and the lowest score was 40.00.

Based on the results of the research data from the pretest and posttest performance results with a sample of 16 Venus Angels female athletes, the pretest average data was 72.7500 with a standard deviation of 6.45497 and the posttest average data

Effectiveness of Self-Talk Training to Improve Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation, and Performance of Venus Angels Futsal Athletes Semarang

was 76.3125 with a standard deviation of 2,47656. The highest pretest performance score is 85.00 and the lowest score is 64.00 while the highest posttest performance score is 88.00 and the lowest score is 68.00.

Table 3. Kolmogorov Smirnov Normality Test

		GPB	GPA	MotB	MotA	KepB	KepA
N		16	16	16	16	16	16
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	72,7500	76,3125	29,6250	34,5000	52,3125	59,0625
	Std. Deviation	6,45497	5,51022	2,65518	2,47656	3,85951	3,51129
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,169	0,200	0,292	0,267	0,118	0,119
	Positive	0,169	0,200	0,292	0,267	0,118	0,119
	Negative	-0,088	-0,105	-0,208	-0,156	-0,084	-0,108
Test Statistic		0,169	0,200	0,292	0,267	0,118	0,119
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}	.086 ^c	.001 ^c	.003 ^c	.200 ^{c,d}	.200 ^{c,d}

The results of the one sample normality test Kolmogorov-Smirnov test using the SPSS application show the Asymp value. Sig (2-tailed) for the performance and self-confidence variables is greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$), then the data is said to be normally distributed while the achievement motivation variable has an Asymp value. Sig (2-tailed) is smaller than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) so the data is said to be not normally distributed. From the results of the normality test, for data that is normally distributed using the t-test and for data that is not normally distributed using the Wilcoxon signed ranks test..

Table 4. T-test results

							Paired Samples Test		
				Paired Differences		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference					
				Lower	Upper				
KepB - KepA	-6,75000	1,69312	0,42328	-7,65220	-5,84780	-15,947	15	0,000	
GPB - GPA	-3,56250	2,27944	0,56986	-4,77713	-2,34787	-6,252	15	0,000	

In the aspect of self-confidence, there is a significant difference in the participants before and after being given the intervention with a value of $t = -15.947$ & $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ (mean \pm SD = 6.75 ± 1.69 , Confidence Interval -7.65 to -5,84). In terms of performance, there was a significant difference between the participants before and after being given the intervention with a value of $t = -6.252$ & $p\text{-value} = 0.000$ (mean \pm SD = 3.56 ± 2.27 , Confidence Interval -4.77 to -2, 34).

Table 5. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test Results

Test Statistics	
	MotA - MotB
Z	-3.601 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0,000

In the aspect of achievement motivation, there is a significant difference in the participants before and after being given the intervention with a Z value of -3.601 with a p value (Asymp. Sig 2 tailed) of 0.000.

DISCUSSION

Self-confidence and achievement motivation are very important things and are needed to achieve maximum performance (Ferdy Irawan & Limanto, 2021). If an athlete has low self-confidence and achievement motivation, it will greatly affect the athlete's performance during competition (Wimala et al., 2019). Psychological factors play an important role in player performance to achieve the desired achievements, 80% of the winning factors for professional athletes are controlled by psychological factors (Grushkoa et al., 2019). Futsal is a very difficult game that relies on difficult tactics and plans in addition to physical challenges (Wijayanti & Kushartanti, 2014). The futsal field, which is relatively small, forces players to think fast and act smart, understanding the strategy and tactics of the coach is something that is not easy, especially to apply it in a match because it is related to the

Effectiveness of Self-Talk Training to Improve Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation, and Performance of Venus Angels Futsal Athletes Semarang

mentality that is influenced by the player's anxiety (Aguss & Yuliandra, 2021). The inability of athletes to understand and develop their capacities can affect their performance when playing (Eubank et al., 2017).

Nevertheless, another factor that made the performance of the players not optimal was the lack of achievement motivation from the Venus Angels players. In the several tournaments that he participated in, there was still no achievement motivation from the players. High achievement motivation will try every troublesome test and game. Athletes who have high motivation within themselves like difficulties in competing, don't give up easily against good opponents and are always optimistic in competing because they want to achieve results like champions in competing (Supriyanto, 2017). Athletes who are confident always think positively to show their best state and increase their confidence in their ability to do so, so they always do this (Abdillah & Ashadi, 2018).

Mental strength has an impact on the appearance of athletes when competing. In sports, confidence is very strong in the appearance of athletes (Prastyo et al., 2017). For athletes, competing is not only a matter of winning and beating the opponent, but also the ability to overcome the fear within themselves. Athletes who are confident always think positively to show their best state and increase their confidence in their ability to do so, so they always do this. The lack of confidence of the Venus Angels players can be seen when they meet difficult opponents. It is very visible that there is still a lack of confidence in the players to win the game and if you have left behind before the goal, it will be difficult to turn things around.

Based on the results of the research that has been done and looking at the statistical descriptive data, it shows that there is an increase in the average before and after being given the Self Talk Training treatment of each variable, namely self-confidence, achievement motivation and athlete performance. The results of the research data from the results of the pretest and posttest of confidence with a sample of 16 athletes, obtained an average pretest data of 52.3125 with a standard deviation of 3.85951 and an average posttest data of 59.0625 with a standard deviation of 3.51129. The achievement motivation variable shows the results of the research data from the pretest and posttest results with a sample of 16 athletes, obtained an average pretest data of 29.6250 with a standard deviation of 2.65518 and a posttest average data of 34.5000 with a standard deviation of 2, 47656. The performance variable shows the results of research data from the pretest and posttest results with a sample of 16 female athletes, obtained an average pretest data of 72.7500 with a standard deviation of 6.45497 and a posttest average data of 76.3125 with a standard deviation of 2, 47656. From these results a hypothesis test was carried out using the T-test and the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and the results of the data analysis conducted, it shows that there was a significant increase before and after being given the Self Talk Training treatment of each variable, namely self-confidence, achievement motivation and athlete performance. After being analyzed with the T-test and Wilcoxon signed rank test, it was concluded that Self-Talk Training was effective in increasing self-confidence, achievement motivation, and performance of futsal athletes of Venus Angels Semarang. Participants before and after being given the intervention. The tests above prove that Self-Talk Training is effective in increasing self-confidence, achievement motivation, and performance of futsal athletes of Venus Angels Semarang.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abdillah, G. D., & Ashadi, K. (2018). Pemahaman pelatih sekolah sepakbola se kota Madiun tentang physiological recovery. *Jurnal Prestasi Olahraga*, 3(1), 1–8.
- 2) Aguss, R. M., & Yuliandra, R. (2021). The effect of hypnotherapy and mental toughness on concentration when competing for futsal athletes. *Medikora*, 20(1), 53–64. <https://doi.org/10.21831/medikora.v20i1.36050>
- 3) Andrini, V. S., & Pratama, H. (2021). Implementasi Quiz Interaktif dengan Software Mentimeter dalam Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar. *Mimbar Ilmu*, 26(2), 287. <https://doi.org/10.23887/mi.v26i2.36923>
- 4) Apriansyah, B., Sulaiman, & Mukarromah, S. B. (2017). Kontribusi Motivasi, Kerjasama, Kepercayaan Diri terhadap Prestasi Atlet Sekolah Sepakbola Pati Training Center di Kabupaten Pati. *Journal of Physical Education and Sports*.
- 5) Effendi, H. (2016). Peranan Psikologi Olahraga Dalam Meningkatkan Prestasi Atlet. *Nusantara (Jurnal Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial)*, 1(1), 23–30.
- 6) Eubank, M., Nesti, M., & Wood, M. L. (2017). A culturally informed approach to mental toughness development in high performance sport. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 48(3), 206–222. <https://doi.org/10.7352/IJSP.2017.48.206>
- 7) Fadillah, R. E. A. (2013). Stres Dan Motivasi Belajar Pada Mahasiswa Psikologi. *Psikoborneo*, 1(3), 148–156.
- 8) Ferdy Irawan, Y., & Limanto, D. (2021). Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosi dan Kesiapan Diri Terhadap Pertandingan Pada Pemain Walet Muda Futsal Academy Kebumen Tahun 2020. *JUMORA: Jurnal Moderasi Olahraga*, 1(1), 18–26.

Effectiveness of Self-Talk Training to Improve Self-Confidence, Achievement Motivation, and Performance of Venus Angels Futsal Athletes Semarang

<https://doi.org/10.53863/mor.v1i01.130>

- 9) Fitria, F. (2018). Pengaruh Latihan Imagery dan Self-Talk Terhadap Konsentrasi dan Ketepatan Tusukan Dalam Permainan Anggar. *Jendela Olahraga*, 3(2), 19–25. <https://doi.org/10.26877/jo.v3i2.2429>
- 10) Grushkoa, A. I., Isaevb, A. V., Kaminskyc, I. V., Leonovd, S. V., & Polikanovae, I. S. (2019). Modern trends of sport psychology in Russian psychological society. *Papeles Del Psicologo*, 40(1), 64–73. <https://doi.org/10.23923/pap.psicol2019.2883>
- 11) Gustian, U. (2016). Pentingnya Perhatian dan Konsentrasi Dalam Menunjang Penampilan Atlet. *Performa Olahraga*, 01, 1–11.
- 12) Jamalong, A. (2014). Peningkatan Prestasi Olahraga Nasional Secara Dini Melalui Pusat Pembinaan Dan Latihan Pelajar (PPLP) Dan Pusat Pembinaan Dan Latihan Mahasiswa (PPLM). *Jurnal Pendidikan Olahraga*, 3(2), 156–168.
- 13) Marhani, I., Sahrani, R., & Monika, S. (2018). Efektivitas Pelatihan Self-Talk Untuk Meningkatkan Harga Diri Remaja Korban Bullying (Studi pada Siswa SMP X Pasar Minggu). *Inspiratif Pendidikan*, 7(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.24252/ip.v7i1.4929>
- 14) Masni, H. (2015). Strategi meningkatkan motivasi belajar mahasiswa. *Dikdaya*, 5(1), 34–45.
- 15) Muhammad, M. (2017). Pengaruh Motivasi Dalam Pembelajaran. *Lantanida Journal*, 4(2), 87. <https://doi.org/10.22373/lj.v4i2.1881>
- 16) Nisa, K., & Jannah, M. (2021). Pengaruh kepercayaan diri terhadap ketangguhan mental atlet bela diri. *Character: Jurnal Penelitian Psikologi*, 8(3), 36–45.
- 17) Nopiyanto, Y. E., & Dimiyati, D. (2018). Karakteristik psikologis atlet Sea Games Indonesia ditinjau dari jenis cabang olahraga dan jenis kelamin. *Jurnal Keolahragaan*, 6(1), 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.21831/jk.v6i1.15010>
- 18) Prastyo, B. W., Sugiyanto, & Doewes, M. (2017). The Development Model of the Basic Techniques of Exercise and Physical Exercise on Futsal Players Level Intermediate. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 2(3), 50–58.
- 19) Putra, M. R. T., & Jannah, M. (2017). Pengaruh Self Talk Positif Terhadap Konsentrasi Pada Atlet Panahan. *Character: Jurnal Penelitian Psikologi*, 4(2), 1–5.
- 20) Rahmansyah, A. K., Khusniyah, A., & Amrozi, Y. (2021). Analisis Manajemen Pengetahuan Terhadap Performa Organisasi. *Jurnal Teknologi Dan Manajemen*, 2(2), 59–64. <https://doi.org/10.31284/j.jtm.2021.v2i2.1460>
- 21) Rohaeni, H. (2016). Model Gaya Kepemimpinan dan Motivasi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai. *Jurnal ECODEMICA*, 4(1), 32–47.
- 22) Sakti, G. F., & Rozali, Y. A. (2015). Hubungan Dukungan Sosial Dengan Kepercayaan Diri Pada Atlet Cabang Olah Raga Taekwondo Dalam Berprestasi (Studi Pada Atlet Taekwondo Club Bjtc, Kabupaten Tangerang). *Jurnal Psikologi Esa Unggul*, 13(1), 26–33.
- 23) Sari, S. (2016). Mengatasi DOMS setelah Olahraga. *Journal Research of Physical Education*.
- 24) Sri Murniyanti. (2020). Pengaruh Motivasi Intrinsik Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Indojaya Agrinusa Tanjung Morawa. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Eka Prasetya: Penelitian Ilmu Manajemen*, 5(2), 45–52. <https://doi.org/10.47663/jmbep.v5i2.32>
- 25) Supriyanto, E. (2017). Hubungan Kematangan Emosi dan Agresifitas Pada Pemain Sepak Bola Remaja Akhir. *Jurnal Psikologi*, 10(2), 183–191.
- 26) Suriani, S., & Lesmana, S. I. (2019). Latihan Theraband Lebih Baik Menurunkan Nyeri Daripada. *Jurnal Fisioterapi*, Volume 13(Nomor 1), 21–25.
- 27) Ulfah, M. (2006). Potensi tumbuhan obat sebagai fitobiotik multi fungsi untuk meningkatkan penampilan dan kesehatan satwa di penangkaran. *Media Konservasi*, 11(3), 109–114.
- 28) Walid, A., Gamal Tamrin Kusumah, R., & Doktoral, P. (2019). *Pengaruh Rasa Percaya Diri Terhadap Motivasi Berprestasi Siswa pada Mata Pelajaran IPA The Effect Of Self Confidence Towards Students' Motivation For Achievements In Science Lesson*. 3.
- 29) Wan Norina Wan Hamat, Zaharah Hussin, Ahmad Fakrudin Mohamed Yusoff, A. A. S. (2013). Pengaruh Media Massa Terhadap Penampilan Akhlak Pelajar Islam Politeknik Malaysia. *The Online Journal of Islamic Education*, 1(1), 17–27.
- 30) Wijayanti, D. I. P. R., & Kushartanti, B. M. W. (2014). Model tes keterampilan dasar futsal bagi pemain KU 10-12 tahun. *Jurnal Keolahragaan*, 2(1), 32–45.
- 31) Wimala, A. S., Doewes, M., & Hidayatullah, M. F. (2019). Development of Dribbling and Shooting Exercise Models in Futsal Sports (Development Study of POK Futsal Achievement Training in Sebelas Maret University). *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, 6(1), 346–352. <https://doi.org/10.18415/ijmmu.v6i1.619>